

Ternary complexes of nickel(II) involving ampicillin and some potentially bi- and tridentate ligands

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The multiple equilibrium studies involved in the Ni^{II}-ampicillin (amp)(A)-1,2-diaminopropane, 1,3-diaminopropane, DL-2,3-diaminopropionic acid, DL-2,4-diaminobutyric acid and DL-2,5-diaminovaleric acid(B) systems show the presence of NiABH₂, NiABH, NiAB and NiABH₋₁ ternary species. In the NiABH₂ species one proton is attached with ligand (A) and the other with ligand (B), while in the NiABH species the site of protonation is ligand (B). In the NiABH₋₁ species the deprotonation occurs with ligand (A). In all these systems, in the NiAB species the binding of the ligands A and B is similar to their binding in their respective binary systems.

We report here the results of investigation on the formation equilibria of Ni^{II}-ampicillin (amp)(A)-1,2-diaminopropanem (dp), 1,3-diaminopropane (tp), DL-2,3-diaminopropionic acid (dapa), DL-2,4-diaminobutyric acid (daba) and DL-2,5-diaminovaleric acid (dava) (B) ternary systems at 37° and *I* = 0.15 mol dm⁻³ (NaClO₄).

Results and Discussion

Ni^{II}-amp(A) binary complex equilibria :

HA, H₂A, NiAH, NiA and NiAH₋₁ species have been identified in this system below pH 8.00 (Table 1). Complex formation of the ligand amp(A) with Ni^{II} was observed at pH 4, where the ligand was exclusively in the ampH form. The log β_{NiA} value (3.58) in this system corresponds to the coordination of amp(A) through *N*-amino and *O*-amide atoms in its NiA species as reported earlier¹.

In the NiAH₋₁ species the only possible source of proton release is the metal-promoted deprotonation of the amide moiety in the Ni(amp)⁺ complex. This type of deprotonation of amp involves a structural change of the type involving the substitution of the amide oxygen atom by the deprotonated amide nitrogen atom¹. This also brings the thiazolidine sulfur atom of the ligand amp in a position suitable for providing axial coordination to Ni^{II}. The coordination via N, N, S in the Ni(H₋₁ amp) is favored by the delocalization of π-electron density of Ni^{II} over to the vacant *p*-orbitals of the sulfur donor atom of the ligand, leading to an increase of electronegativity of the coordinated Ni^{II}.

Table 1. Stability constants for the proton and parent binary complexes of Ni^{II} with dp, tp, dapa, daba and dava(B)

Parameter	amp	dp ^a	tp ^a	dapa ^a	daba ^a	dava ^a
log β _{HB}	4.69(1)	9.87(2)	9.99(1)	9.37(2)	9.93(2)	10.22(1)
log β _{H₂B}	9.72(5)	17.01(1)	18.31(4)	15.98(3)	18.02(4)	18.85(2)
log β _{H₁B}	—	—	—	17.37(5)	19.88(6)	20.99(4)
log β _{NiBH}	8.89(9)	12.29(4)	13.45(5)	13.71(3)	14.43(3)	14.89(3)
log β _{NiB}	3.58(6)	6.95(5)	5.96(7)	8.47(3)	8.77(1)	7.38(9)
log β _{NiB₂H₂}	—	—	—	—	—	29.13(4)
log β _{NiB₂H}	—	18.89(7)	—	21.61(4)	22.42(5)	—
log β _{NiB₂}	—	13.07(8)	11.28(9)	15.77(3)	15.57(3)	13.33(8)
log β _{NiB₃}	—	17.13(2)	—	—	—	—
log β _{NiAH₋₁}	-4.64(8)	—	—	—	—	—
pK _{NiBH} ^{II}	5.31	5.34	7.49	5.24	5.66	7.51
pK _{NiB₂H} ^{II}	—	5.82	—	5.84	6.85	—
pK _{NiAH₋₁} ^{II}	8.22	—	—	—	—	—
log K _{NiB₂} ^{NiB}	—	6.12	5.32	7.30	6.80	5.95
log K _{NiB₂H} ^{NiBH}	—	6.60	—	7.90	7.99	—
log K _{NiB₃} ^{NiB₂}	—	4.06	—	—	—	—

*amp becomes ligand A in the mixed ligand systems.

^aRef. 8.

The NiAH type of species has been found to be more favored at low pH values. In this species the extra proton can attach either to the carboxylato group or to the primary amino group of amp. The pK_{NiAH}^{II} value (5.31) follows the trend of the log β_{HA} value of amp(A) indicating the possibility of the attachment of the extra proton with the amino group of the ligand.

In this binary system at lower pH values the color of the solution is green which gets intensified and then yellow to pink at higher pH values. This clearly suggests structural realignment of the complex formed. The electronic spectrum has been taken by mixing the metal ion and the ligand in the ratio of 1 : 2 at pH 6.5 and 8.0 where NiA and NiAH₁ species have been found to have maximum concentration. The λ_{max} values of 495, 465 and 415 observed for the NiA amp complex at pH 6.5 experiences a blue-shift at pH 8.0, which is due to the formation of NiAH₁ species. The λ_{max} values for NiAH₁ amp species are 490, 460 and 410, which are in good agreement with the values reported earlier¹.

Ternary complex equilibria :

The analysis of the pH-titration data shows the presence of NiAB₂, NiABH, NiAB and NiAH₁B complexes in the Ni^{II}-amp(A)-dapa and -daba(B) systems, NiABH₂, NiABH and NiAB in the Ni^{II}-amp(A)-tp(B) system, and NiABH and NiAB complexes in the Ni^{II}-amp(A)-dp and -dava(B) systems (Table 2) in addition to various binary species due to ligands A and B (Table 1).

Table 2. Stability constants for the Ni^{II}-amp(A)-dp, tp, dapa, daba and dava(B) ternary systems

Parameter	dp	tp	dapa	daba	dava
Temp = 37 ^o , I = 0.15 mol dm ⁻³ (NaClO ₄)					
log β _{NiABH₂}	—	21.82(8)	22.51(3)	23.02(7)	—
log β _{NiABH}	16.48(2)	17.56(6)	17.86(8)	19.19(3)	19.05(8)
log β _{NiAB}	10.98(6)	10.73(2)	11.99(1)	12.52(2)	11.06(5)
log β _{NiAH₁B}	—	—	3.58(8)	3.77(9)	—
pK _{NiAH₁B}	—	—	8.41	8.25	—
pK _{NiABH₂}	—	4.26	4.65	4.43	—
pK _{NiABH}	5.60	7.63	5.87	6.67	7.99
log K _{NiABH} ^{NiB}	4.19	4.11	4.15	4.76	4.16
log K _{NiAB} ^{NiA}	7.40	7.15	8.41	8.44	7.48
log K _{NiAB} ^{NiB}	4.03	4.77	3.52	3.75	3.68
log K _{NiAH₁B}	—	—	8.22	8.41	—
Δ log K _{NiABH₂}	—	-0.52	-0.09	0.34	—
Δ log K _{NiABH}	0.61	0.53	0.57	1.18	0.58
Δ log K _{NiAB}	0.45	1.19	-0.06	0.17	0.10
Δ log K _{NiAH₁B}	—	—	-0.25	-0.36	—

Stability and structure of NiAB complexes : The log K_{NiAB}^{NiB} values (Table 2) of all these systems are comparable to the log K₁ value of the Ni^{II}-amp(A) binary system (Table 1). This suggests that amp binds the metal ion in the NiAB ternary and NiA binary species in a similar manner, i.e. via *N*-amino and *O*-amide atoms. Again, the log K_{NiAB}^{NiA} values in the Ni^{II}-amp(A)-dp and -tp(B) systems (Table 2) correspond to the bidentate binding of dp and tp(B) in their respective NiAB complexes. Thus, the NiAB species in the Ni^{II}-amp(A)-dp and -tp(B) systems will be tetracoordinated. The Δ log K_{NiAB} value (+1.19) in the Ni^{II}-amp(A)-tp(B) system is more positive compared to that of 0.45 in the corresponding dp(B) system. This indicates higher

stability for the 5- and 6-membered chelate rings in the former system compared to the 5- and 5-membered chelates in the latter system.

In the Ni^{II}-amp(A)-dapa(B) system, the log β_{NiAB} value (11.99) is higher than that of 10.88 in the dp(B) system. This demonstrates that dapa(B) binds the metal ion in a tridentate manner in its NiAB. Similarly, the higher log β_{NiAB} value (12.52) of the Ni^{II}-amp(A)-daba(B) system compared to that of tp(B) system (10.73) indicates the tridentate binding of daba in its NiAB species. The log K_{NiAB}^{NiA} value obtained in the Ni^{II}-amp(A)-dava system is comparable to the log K₁ value in the Ni^{II}-dava(B) system, demonstrating that in the NiAB species dava binds in a tridentate mode similar to its binding in the NiB binary species.

Stability and structure of NiAH₁B complexes : Only in the Ni^{II}-amp(A)-dapa and -daba(B) systems, this type of species has been detected. The pK_{NiAH₁B}^H values (Table 2) are in the same range and follow the trend of pK_{NiAH₁}^H values in the Ni^{II}-amp(A) system (Table 1). The log K_{NiAH₁B}^{NiA} values (Table 2) in both the dapa and daba(B) systems bear favorable comparison to the corresponding log K₁ values in the Ni^{II}-dapa and -daba(B) systems. This suggests that the deprotonation occurs with the amp(A). Thus, the deprotonated amp(A) ligand binds the metal ion via the *N*-amino, *N*-deprotonated amide and sulfur atoms, and the B ligands dapa and daba bind the metal ion in a tridentate manner giving a coordination number of six to the metal ion in the NiAH₁B species.

Stability and structure of NiABH₂ and NiABH complexes : The pK_{NiABH}^H values (Table 2) are not comparable to each other and these values follow the trends of the respective pK_{NiBH}^H values (Table 1). This demonstrates that the site of protonation is with the ligand(B). By considering the site of protonation in the NiBH binary species², it can be concluded that the extra proton in the NiABH species in the Ni^{II}-amp(A)-dp and -tp(B) systems resides with one of the amino groups of the dp/tp(B), and in the Ni^{II}-amp(A)-dapa, daba and dava(B) systems, the extra proton is attached with the terminal amino group of the respective (B) ligand. In all systems, the trend in the log K_{NiABH}^{NiB} values (Table 2) indicates that amp(A) ligand binds the metal ion in the NiABH species in a bidentate manner.

The diprotonated species NiABH₂ has been detected in appreciable amounts in the Ni^{II}-amp(A)-tp, -dapa and -daba(B) systems below pH 6.5. In these complexes, it can be expected that of the two protons, one would be attached with amp(A) ligand and the other with the respective (B) ligands.

Experimental

All the ligands used were Fluka products of Puriss quality. $\text{Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and other reagents were prepared and estimated as described earlier³. The experimental procedure for the pH-metric studies has been described earlier⁴. All the calculations were done with the aid of the computer program⁵ MINQUAD-75 on a HCl HP infinity computer. The auxiliary data for the Ni^{II} -amp(A) system were redetermined in the present experimental conditions, while such data in the Ni^{II} -dp, tp, dapa, daba and dava(B) systems taken from literature (Table 1). The electronic spectral measurement was carried out following the earlier proce-

dure³ using Perkin-Elmer Lambda 3B spectrophotometer.

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